

**PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL FEATURES OF FORMING PROFILING
COMPETENCE IN FUTURE OFFICERS**

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Abstract: This article analyzes the psychological features of forming profiling competence in future officers from a scientific and pedagogical perspective. In the context of modern military service, the ability to analyze human behavior, emotional states, and verbal as well as nonverbal actions is substantiated as an important component of an officer's professional activity. The psychological essence of profiling competence, its structural components, psychological mechanisms, and effective methods for developing this competence in future officers are discussed. In addition, the significance of profiling technologies in the early identification of stress, conflicts, dangerous situations, and psychological threats is revealed. The article also describes the pedagogical and psychological conditions for the formation of profiling competence based on the competence-based approach, learner-centered education, psychological analysis, and reflective approaches.

Keywords: profiling, psychological stability, officer, competence, nonverbal communication, psychological analysis, emotional intelligence, reflection, stress, military psychology.

The modern global security environment, the intensification of information-psychological threats, the expansion of hybrid warfare, and the decisive role of the human factor in military management create completely new requirements for the professional and psychological training of officer personnel. Today, the military service process requires not only a high level of combat training, but also a deep understanding of human psychology, the ability to analyze personal behavior, anticipate potential threats, and make the right decisions in stressful situations. From this point of view, the competence of profiling is an important psychological and pedagogical component in the professional competence of future officers. The concept of profiling is interpreted as a special psychological technology aimed at analyzing a person's internal psychological state through his external movements, facial expressions, pantomime, speech, emotional reactions, and psychophysiological signs. From a scientific point of view, profiling allows you to assess a person's emotional state, psychological characteristics, potential intentions, and level of danger through a comprehensive analysis of verbal and nonverbal signs of human behavior. This is especially important in the military field, since an officer's ability to quickly and accurately assess human psychology is an important factor in ensuring security in emergency situations, preventing conflicts, and maintaining collective psychological stability.

The formation of profiling competence in future officers is primarily associated with the development of a high level of psychological observation in them. Observation is the ability to quickly perceive the slightest changes in human behavior, emotional reactions, and psychological states such as signs of stress or anxiety. In the process of military activity, an officer must be able to quickly identify the actions, changes in speech, emotional state, and signs of mental tension of those around him. This process is closely related to the stability of attention, sensory sensitivity, and the ability to analyze psychologically.

Another important psychological characteristic of profiling competence is emotional intelligence. In modern psychological research, emotional intelligence is considered as a person's ability to understand and manage his own emotions and correctly assess the emotional state of others. An officer with developed emotional intelligence correctly assesses the psychological environment in the team, anticipates conflicts that may arise in interpersonal relationships, and is

able to maintain emotional stability in stressful situations. Therefore, the development of emotional intelligence in future officers is one of the important psychological tasks in the process of forming profiling competence. The ability to analyze analytical thinking and psychological forecasting also plays an important role in the development of this competence. Since profiling is based on assessing a person's internal psychological state through his external actions, the officer is required to analyze various verbal and nonverbal signals and draw certain conclusions. This process requires the ability to understand cause-and-effect relationships, analyze data, think logically, and predict potential danger. In this regard, profiling competence serves to develop cognitive activity and analytical thinking in future officers.

Modern military service is characterized by a high level of stress factors. Constant danger, psychological pressure, the need to make emergency decisions have a strong impact on the human psyche. Therefore, the process of forming a profile competence is inextricably linked with the development of stress tolerance and psychological stability. The ability to objectively assess human behavior in stressful conditions, control the emotional state and objectively analyze the situation is one of the important professional qualities of an officer. This requires the formation of willpower, emotional control and mental balance. Reflective thinking is of particular importance in the formation of profiling competence. Reflection means the ability to analyze a person's own actions, decisions and psychological state. In the process of profiling, an officer must be able to evaluate not only the psychological state of others, but also his own activities. This allows him to understand mistakes, analyze the effectiveness of decision-making and improve professional activity. The reflective approach provides future officers with independent thinking, psychological self-control and professional growth.

The issue of forming profiling competence is closely related to the theories of psychology, pedagogy, cognitive sciences and military education. The theoretical foundations of this competence are explained by a number of scientific concepts that study human behavior, the process of communication and psychophysiological reactions.

In the development of the science of psychology, ideas for analyzing human behavior were scientifically substantiated by such scientists as Z. Freud, K. Jung, B.F. Skinner, J. Piaget, L.S. Vygotsky, A.N. Leontiev. In particular, L.S. Vygotsky, analyzing the relationship between the human psyche and the social environment, emphasizes the decisive importance of communication and social influence in the development of the individual. This scientifically substantiates the possibility of understanding the internal psychological state of a person through his external behavior in the process of profiling.

A.N. According to Leontiev's theory of activity, the human psyche is formed and manifested in the process of activity. Profiling technology is also based on the analysis of human actions, speech, emotional reactions and the process of communication. Thus, human activity is an important source of understanding his internal psychological state.

Also, the theory of emotional intelligence plays an important role in the theoretical foundations of profiling competence. D. Goleman interprets emotional intelligence as a person's ability to manage his own emotions, understand the feelings of others and correctly organize emotional relationships. In the activities of a modern officer, emotional intelligence is of great importance in assessing the collective psychological environment, managing conflicts and making stable decisions under stressful conditions.

Profiling competence is an integrative psychological and pedagogical structure, which expresses the ability to analyze, evaluate and predict human behavior, emotional state and psychological characteristics. The formation of this competence is closely related to a number of psychological processes.

First, the profile requires a high level of observation. Observation is the ability to perceive the slightest changes in a person's external actions, which is based on the stability of attention and psychological sensitivity. A modern officer must be able to quickly detect signs of stress, anxiety, aggression or deception in human behavior. This requires a high level of mental activity.

Cognitive processes also play an important role in the profiling process. The analysis of a person's speech, facial expressions, gestures, and emotional reactions depends on the ability to think analytically and understand cause-and-effect relationships. Therefore, profiling competence is considered an important component of cognitive competence.

At the same time, profiling competence is also inextricably linked with emotional intelligence. Emotional intelligence includes a person's ability to: understand their own emotions, manage their emotional state, understand the feelings of others, and regulate emotional relationships.

An officer with developed emotional intelligence quickly understands the psychological state of people and can effectively use psychological influence tools in communication.

The use of innovative pedagogical technologies is important in the formation of profiling competence in future officers. In particular, simulation exercises, case technologies, role-playing games, stress-modeled situations, and debriefing technology allow for the effective development of this competence. Through simulation exercises, trainees acquire the skills of analyzing human behavior, identifying potential threats, and making quick decisions in conditions close to real situations. Case technologies, on the other hand, develop analytical thinking by analyzing situations with conflict or psychological threats.

Innovative pedagogical technologies play an important role in the formation of profiling competence in the modern military education system. In particular, simulation exercises, case technologies, role-playing games, debriefing technology, and stress-modeled situations are highly effective.

Simulation exercises develop psychological analysis and quick decision-making skills in future officers by creating conditions close to real situations. Such exercises provide the opportunity to observe changes in human behavior, identify psychological threats, and quickly assess the situation.

Case technologies are one of the effective tools for developing profiling competence. Through cases, listeners analyze various psychological situations, evaluate conflict situations, and make decisions to solve the problem.

In particular, debriefing technology is an important pedagogical and psychological tool in the formation of profiling competence. During the debriefing process, future officers analyze practical actions, understand mistakes made, assess the psychological state, and draw conclusions on improving future activities. This serves to develop reflective thinking, strengthen psychological stability, and enrich professional experience.

Also, studying non-verbal communication tools is important in the development of profiling competence. A person's facial expressions, gestures, eye movements, speech tempo, and intonation provide important information about his internal emotional state. By analyzing these signs, future officers acquire the ability to draw psychological conclusions about a person's mental state and possible intentions.

In conclusion, the formation of profiling competence in future officers is one of the important directions of modern military education. This competence is of great importance in psychological analysis of human behavior, early detection of danger, making the right decisions in stressful situations, and ensuring collective psychological stability. In the process of forming profiling competence, observation, emotional intelligence, analytical thinking, stress tolerance, and a reflective approach are decisive psychological factors. At the same time, the use of

simulation exercises, case technologies, and debriefing methods allows for the effective development of professional and psychological training of future officers.

References

1. Пол Экман. *Психология лжи. Обмани меня, если сможешь*. — Санкт-Петербург: Питер, 2010.
2. Пол Экман. *Узнай лжеца по выражению лица*. — Москва: Эксмо, 2013.
3. Джо Наварро. *Я вижу, о чём вы думаете*. — Москва: Попурри, 2012.
4. Военная психология и педагогика / тахрири остида А. Г. Маклаков. — Санкт-Петербург: Питер, 2005.
5. Профайлинг. Технологии предотвращения противоправных действий. — Москва, 2016